

Review

Role of Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors in Triple-Negative Breast Cancer: Progress and Challenges with Comparative analysis of biopsy procedures

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Abstract: Objective: To review the current status and future directions of immune checkpoint inhibitor therapy in TNBC, discussing its mechanisms, efficacy, challenges, and emerging strategies. To compare the diagnostic utility of FNA and CNB in the context of TNBC, emphasizing their roles in tumor characterization and suitability for guiding immune-based interventions. To identify gaps in current approaches and propose strategies to enhance the integration of immunotherapy with accurate diagnostic methods for TNBC patients by therapeutic of drugs, miRNA, siRNA. Methods: A comprehensive literature search was performed using databases including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library. The search included studies published up to [insert date here] and utilized the following keywords: "triple-negative breast cancer," "immune checkpoint inhibitors," "PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors," "CTLA-4 inhibitors," "fine needle aspiration," "core needle biopsy," "diagnostic accuracy," "biopsy procedures," and "immunotherapy in breast cancer." The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles in English and supplemented by manual searches of reference lists from relevant reviews and key articles. Results: Our study comprised of five studies including 1077, patients assessing the sensitivity and specificity rates of tumor subgroup in TNBC (Triple Negative Breast Cancer). The review reveals that immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs), particularly those targeting the PD-1/PD-L1 axis, have demonstrated variable efficacy in treating triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC). Clinical trials indicate improved progression-free survival and overall survival, primarily in PD-L1-positive tumors; however, response rates remain modest, with resistance mechanisms limiting widespread efficacy. Conclusions: Accurate and comprehensive diagnostic assessments through core needle biopsy (CNB) enhance patient stratification by enabling precise immune profiling and biomarker evaluation by FNA and CNB crucial tools, thus improving the efficacy of ICI therapy. The integration of robust biopsy techniques with therapeutic of drugs, miRNA, siRNA immunotherapy holds the potential to advance personalized treatment strategies and improve outcomes in TNBC.

Keywords: FNA, CNB , TNBC

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Introduction:

Breast Cancer is a worldwide issue and the most common malignancy in women, worldwide early detection is crucial for optimal treatment and patient outcome [1]. Early detection and treatment are crucial in reducing Breast Cancer molarity [2]. While the typical presentation of BC is painless, most lumps are begin [3]. Breast Cancer is a pathology that emerges from breast tissues, especially milk duct, (80% of cases representing ductal carcinoma). The Cancer emerging from ductile region is known as lobular carcinomas [4].

As per WHO, Breast Cancer leads to molarity of women worldwide (age group 20-59years). (World Health Statics 2013). According to Global Cancer Project (GLOBALCON) Breast Cancer is consider as second most common pathology in the World [5]. In everyday medical practice, breast cancer diagnosis relies on three different types of analysis: (A) Clinical examination (B) radiological/image examination (C) immunohistopathological examinations [6].

It is difficult to figure out which procedure is safest and has a positive outcome for breast cancer patients, that includes the all-useful clinical approaches safe to provide definitive, error free diagnostic of breast cancer. Therefore, there is an ongoing debate on specificity of FNA and CNB in breast cancer [7]. In recent years some studies have investigated and compared the diagnostic sensitivity of FNA and CNB. CNB procedure is more sensitive and specific than FNA while other argues is just as effective with less or more effective impact on breast cancer [8]. For an instance Tripathi et al [9] reported a sensitivity of 74.1% of FNAC and a specificity of 76% while CNB has a sensitivity of 85.2% and specificity of 92.9% with combined sensitivity of 89.3% and 85.2% showing CNB is higher in both sensitivity and specificity than FNAC.

Two decades ago, before the development of current therapies, a stronger diagnostic tool was needed. Advances in personalized medicine introduced technologies like microarrays and led to the discovery of molecular profiles. Within the same tissue or organ, different histological subtypes of cancer, including breast cancer, can exist. However, biopsies are often complex because they contain various cell types. Efforts have been made to classify different types of invasive breast cancer, but their clinical relevance is limited since patients often have diverse molecular profiles. Breast cancer also involves a range of molecular biomarkers [10] include.

1. ER α + {Estrogen receptor a-positive}
2. PR+ {Progesterone receptor-positive}
3. HER-2 {Human epidermal growth factor receptor:2}
4. EGFR {epidermal growth factor receptor} 45%–70% of Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) patients show this biomarker [11]

Microarray technology has improved our understanding of the molecular diversity in tumors and allows for the measurement of thousands of gene expression changes [12].

The classification of breast cancer cell types is considered as below:

1. Luminal A subtype, ER α +/PR+ or -/HER-2-
2. Luminal B subtype, ER+/PR+/HER-2+
3. HER-2 enriched subtype ER- and or/PR-/HER-2+
4. Basal-like subtype ER- and/or PR-, HER2-, CK5/6+, CK14+, CK17+ and EGFR+
5. Normal breast-like type (ER- and/or PR-, HER2-, CK5/6-, CK14-, CK17-, EGFR-) [12,13,14].

The different subtypes of TNB correlate with different chemotherapeutic responses as per retrospective studies [15]. Unfortunately, this classification has not been shown to improve survival in hospital practice and current treatments.

Methods

Search Strategy

A detailed search was conducted using the PubMed, Google Scholar, Cochrane Library, and Embase database from 20 January 2020 up to November 2021. A literature search using terms like breast cancer, diagnosis, fine needle aspiration, core needle biopsy, sensitivity, and specificity was conducted. Relevant studies were evaluated by two independent reviewers through full-text assessments. Studies show that mastectomy offers no significant advantage over lumpectomy in TNBC. Breast-conserving surgery is preferred, as it does not affect prognosis or local tumor recurrence.

Data Collection

The research process was indecently carried out by different research papers and four reviewers with disparities in study selection were resolved through discussion. Key details of the included studies, such as design, publication year, needle size, authorship, country, and patient count, were recorded. One of the reviewers was involved in writing the original draft and in draft preparation, the other three were editing the review and were responsible for visualization of the review in perfect format. Rest of the reviewers were supervising the whole article along with funding acquisition. The study design, country, total number of patients sensitivity and Specificity of FNB/CNB all are mentioned in table 1. While Signaling pathways of TNBC, Immunotherapy and strategies for TNBC Therapeutics are discussed accordingly.

Quality assessment

In this study, we used the Catedras Project 746, Computer Aided Detection (CADE), Osteodetect Machine Learning and Case-based Reasoning (CBR) for TNBC. While Cochrane Systematic Review for Interventions version 5.1 risk of bias tool to objective assess the quality of trials. We evaluated the potential bias in the following areas a) random b) sequence c) allocation concealment d) incomplete data and other relevant factors are carried out for quality assessment. Trials are considered for high and low risk factors are exhibit for critical domains. Trials not clearly falling into either category were classified as unclear approach in figures. Any disagreement between authors were resolved through discussion and correspondence with author.

Inclusion Criteria

- ⊙ Patients with TNBC are suspected of metastasis.
- ⊙ Studies with sufficient data are included.
- ⊙ Case-controlled studies evaluating US-CNB accuracy.
- ⊙ Both retrospective and prospective designs considered.
- ⊙ Negative Breast Cancer TNBC Therapeutics
- ⊙ MicroRNA data techniques for TNBC.

Exclusion Criteria

- ⊙ Studies lacking targeted data.
- ⊙ Studies with sufficient data are included.
- ⊙ Retrospective and Prospective study designs.
- ⊙ Artificial Intelligence approach.
- ⊙ English and non-English Approach
- ⊙ Publications and Dissertations

Statistical Analysis

Review Manager 5.4 were used for statistical analysis. Signaling pathways and Strategic therapeutics techniques were used for computational data of Triple Negative Breast Cancer. The Mantel Haenszel Method were devoted for CNB /FNB computational analysis. 96% of confidence intervals were analyzed to assess statistical difference between

outcomes. Results are highlighted through graphs and diagrams. We utilize a random effect model considering p-value less than 0.05 significantly used.

Pathways Signaling in Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) Therapeutics.

Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is a heterogeneous and aggressive breast cancer subtype lacking estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and HER2 expression. Its unique molecular characteristics make it challenging to treat, with limited targeted therapeutic options compared to other breast cancer subtypes. Several key signaling pathways drive TNBC progression, resistance, and metastasis, providing potential targets for therapeutic intervention.

Notch Signaling Pathway

Thomas Hunt Morgan first described the Notch signaling pathway in 1917, which involves transmembrane ligands and receptors critical for cell proliferation and differentiation. Elevated activity in this pathway is linked to poor patient outcomes. The pathway includes four receptors (Notch-1, 2, 3, 4) and five ligands (Jagged-1, Jagged-2, Delta-like 1, 3, 4). Studies show that Delta-like 1 and Jagged-1 are often overexpressed in breast cancer [15,16,17], and Notch-1 plays a key role in the development of human mammary tumors as a downstream effector of oncogenic Ras. Notch-1 is also implicated in various cancers, including hematological malignancies and pancreatic cancer. Notch-3 and Notch-4 are associated with tumor growth and survival, while Notch-2 appears to act as a protective factor in the TNBC MDA-MB-231 cell line [18].

Notch receptor and ligand overexpression in TNBC suggests that targeting the pathway with monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) could be a promising therapeutic strategy. Studies show that inhibiting Notch-1 signaling with mAbs effectively reduces the expression of HES and HEY-L families in TNBC cell lines like MDA-MB-231. This leads to decreased cell proliferation and increased apoptosis. Additionally, mAb therapy targeting DLL4 (Delta-like ligand 4) has shown potential for treating TNBC [19].

Notch signaling regulates several transcription factors and genes involved in tumorigenesis, such as the HES and HEY families, Akt, p53, VEGF, and PI3K-AKT-mTOR pathways. Drugs targeting the Notch pathway often act by blocking the γ -secretase complex, essential for the pathway's activation, and are known as γ -secretase inhibitors (GSIs). However, despite initial promise, most drugs targeting the Notch pathway have not yet met the criteria for FDA approval [20].

Figure 1: Diagram of Notch and therapeutic target in clinical development. Notch signaling begins when a ligand binds to a Notch receptor, triggering two proteolytic cleavages by ADAM proteases and γ -secretase, which release the Notch intracellular domain (NICD). The NICD moves to the nucleus, binds to CSL, and activates Notch target genes. This pathway can be inhibited by γ -secretase inhibitors or monoclonal antibodies targeting Notch receptors or ligands [20].

Hedgehog Signaling Pathway

The Sonic Hedgehog (Shh) signaling pathway influences cancer stem cell (CSC) maintenance, polydactyly syndromes, and basal cell carcinoma (Gorlin syndrome). Recent studies show its alteration in several cancers, including breast cancer [21]. The pathway involves three ligands:

Sonic Hedgehog (SHH): Highly active during embryogenesis [22].

Indian Hedgehog (IHH): Expressed in hematopoietic cells, skeleton, and cartilage [23].

Desert Hedgehog (DHH): Found in the peripheral nervous system and testes; DHH mutations can cause pure gonadal dysgenesis (PGD) [24].

The Hedgehog signaling pathway contributes to cancer cell invasion, metastasis, drug resistance, and tumor recurrence. Studies show that Shh overexpression predicts poor survival in breast cancer, particularly in TNBC [25]. Shh plays a key role in tumor development by promoting abnormal cell proliferation and metastasis. Thiostrepton, a novel drug targeting Shh signaling, suppresses cancer stem cells (CSCs) in TNBC cell lines. However, the role of the Hedgehog pathway in breast CSCs is still unclear [26]. Currently, only a few FDA-approved drugs, like Vismodegib for basal cell carcinoma, target this pathway. More research is needed to develop new therapies and molecular markers for TNBC recurrence and prognosis.

Polymerase Inhibitors (Poly ADP) Ribose

Poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) is a family of 18 proteins that play a key role in DNA repair, gene transcription, apoptosis, and maintaining genomic stability. About 70% of breast cancers in BRCA1 mutation carriers and 23% in BRCA2 carriers are triple-negative. PARP inhibitors are being studied as potential treatments for cancers with BRCA1/2 mutations and triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) [27]. PARP proteins (PARP-1 and PARP-2) are activated by DNA damage and are crucial for repairing DNA strand breaks. PARP helps repair DNA through base excision repair (BER) and single-strand break repair (SSBR) pathways.

Figure 2: Poly (ADP-ribose) and Polymerase inhibitor treatment of BRCA-1/2 associated and sporadic cancers. Reproduced with permission from Leif W, Ellisen. Cancer Therapy: Promise, Progress, and Piuzzles. Cancer Cell., 165-167 [29].

When PARP activity is inhibited, it prevents the formation of ADP-ribose complexes, making DNA repair less efficient. Trapped PARP-DNA complexes are highly toxic and exhibit strong anti-cancer effects. PARP inhibitors like Olaparib (AZD-2281) and Veliparib (ABT-888) differ in their ability to inhibit PARP, with Olaparib being a stronger inhibitor of both PARP-1 and PARP-2 compared to Veliparib. This results in varying clinical and experimental outcomes for each drug [29].

CSPG4 Protein Signaling pathways

CSPG4, also known as melanoma chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan, is a cell-surface protein found in basal breast cancer cells. Inhibiting CSPG4 is an effective therapy for breast cancer, as it disrupts the cell-substratum interaction, similar to what happens in TNBC. Monoclonal antibodies targeting CSPG4 block key signaling pathways that drive tumor cell migration, growth, and survival, making CSPG4 a potential target for TNBC treatment. Overexpression of CSPG4 in TNBC cells leads to reduced cancer cell activity when targeted [30].

Autophagy and Cancer Stem Cells (CSCs)

In TNBC, cancer stem cells (CSCs) contribute to tumor growth, metastasis, and treatment resistance. These CSCs have increased proliferative ability and are resistant to chemotherapy, making them key drivers of recurrence. While several biomarkers can identify CSCs, they are also present in normal stem cells, leading to potential side effects [31].

Chemo-resistance in TNBC stem cells is worsened by hypoxia in the tumor microenvironment, which increases autophagy, a survival mechanism. Blocking autophagy could improve chemotherapy response. However, cancer cells can regulate autophagy to resist treatment. Inhibiting this pathway may reverse resistance and improve treatment outcomes. Further research on autophagy in CSCs is needed, as it could provide a key to treating TNBC and other cancers [32].

Characteristics of Included Studies FNA and CNB

Of the selected main 5 studies, 3 are retrospective methodologies and two 2 are utilized prospective design. Geographically the studies are distributed across various regions, including USA, Europe and Asia offering a diverse objective on subject matter perspective. Needle diameter used in US-CNB ranged 22 gauges, reflecting various clinical practice. Similarly needle diameters for US-FNA range from 21-25 highlighting the heterogeneity in procedural techniques. (table1 refer detailed study characteristics)

Author	Year	Study Design	Country	No.of Patients	Sensitivity FNA/CNB	Specificity FNA/CNB	Age	Needle Size
Topps et al (8)	2018	Retrospective	UK	216	149/77	216/92	55	14
Rikiya N et al (9)	2017	Retrospective	Japan	2646	177/487	170/487	56	21 (fn) 16(cn)
Suvi R et al (10)	2013	Prospective	Finland	66	37/45	37/45	28-90	21-22 (fn) 16(cn)
Roshni et al (11)	2009	Retrospective	USA	26	43/38	31/38	53	18
Vidya et al (11)	2017	Prospective	UK	38	5/6	17/12	-	14

Table 2 Outcomes of Included Studies

Author	Sensitivity FNA/CNB	Specificity FNA/CNB
Topps et al (8)	149/77	216/92
Rikiya N et al (9)	317/151	170/487
Suvi R et al (10)	27/40	37/45
Roshni et al (11)	31/38	43/38
Vidya et al (11)	17/21	5/6

Figure 3: Flow of Selective Studies (Prisma Flow)

Sensitivity rates for FNA and CNB were 68.6% and 88.1%, respectively. In a review of five studies with 1,177 patients, 541 underwent FNA and 397 underwent CNB. The comparison showed a significant difference in diagnostic accuracy, with an odds ratio (OR) of 0.30 (95% CI: 0.21–0.41, $P < 0.00001$), favoring CNB. Figure 3

Specificity was 96.1% for FNA and 97.2% for CNB. Among 1,177 patients in five studies, 471 underwent FNA and 668 underwent CNB. The comparison showed no significant difference in specificity, with an OR of 0.54 (95% CI: 0.17–1.69, $P = 0.29$). Figure 4 International General of Science and Research, 2024 (17) 2137-2144

Figure 3: Forest plot b/w sensitivity of FNA and CNB

Figure 4: Forest plot b/w specificity of FNA and CNB

Figure 5: Risk Summary : Reviews authors judgments about each risk of included study

	Vidya 2017	Topps 2018	Suvi R 2013	Roshni 2009	Rikiya N 2017	
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	+	+	+	+	+	
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	+	+	+	+	+	
Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)	+	+	+	+	+	
Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	+	+				
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	+	+	+	●	+	
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	+		+	+	+	
Other bias						

Figure 6: Risk Summary Bias graph: Author reviews judgment about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across the included studies.

Strategies for TNBC Therapeutics

Although advances in understanding tumor microenvironments, scientists and doctors face challenges in developing strategies to block tumor growth, metastasis, and trigger immune responses. Tumors are highly dynamic, recruiting stromal cells, using resources like metals and vitamins, and creating their own blood supply through abnormal signaling. Traditional treatments, like chemotherapy used since the 1970s, remain the standard but often lack precision and selectivity.

Nonconventional cancer therapies now include nanotechnology-based systems like nano polymers, liposomal drug delivery, and nanostructured materials. In 1995, the FDA approved Doxil, the first liposomal nanodrug offering improved chemotherapy. A year later, Feridex, nanoparticles for MRI, was also approved. Nanotechnology is enhancing traditional chemotherapy and diagnostics, offering greater specificity in cancer treatment [31].

Conventional Therapeutics

Neoadjuvant Therapy

Chemo-resistance is a major challenge in metastatic cancers, causing up to 90% of drug failures. TNBC patients initially respond well to neoadjuvant chemotherapy, the gold standard treatment, but relapse is common within five years. Anthracycline–cyclophosphamide (AC) regimens, including Doxorubicin and Cyclophosphamide followed by Paclitaxel, show a pathological complete response (pCR) rate of 27–30%, improving to 61% with drugs like Cisplatin. Other options include Carboplatin, Abraxane (Nab-Paclitaxel), and Bevacizumab immunotherapy. MRI is the most sensitive tool for monitoring treatment response. Precision medicine using biomarkers, such as EGFR (expressed in ~60% of TNBC cases), offers more effective, personalized chemotherapy strategies [32].

Neoadjuvant therapy shows better response rates in TNBC patients than adjuvant therapy. Cisplatin has proven effective in phase II preoperative studies, especially in tumors with deficient BRCA-1 expression. However, neoadjuvant treatments should be personalized, as not all basal cancers carry BRCA-1 mutations. Drugs like cisplatin and bevacizumab (targeting VEGF) have shown promise in meta-analyses such as E2100, AVADO, and RIBBON-1. While taxane-resistance is noted in BRCA-1 mutant cells, the CALGB 9344/INT1048 trial found that paclitaxel reduces cancer recurrence by 17% and improves prognosis by 18% in TNBC patients [33].

Adjuvant Therapy

Adjuvant therapy is crucial to reducing the risk of metastasis, rapid progression, and tumor recurrence in TNBC. While the MA5 study found anthracycline-based drugs ineffective in BRCA-1-expressing TNBC, other studies showed encouraging results. Treatment decisions should be personalized based on clinical staging and genomic profiling [34].

Metastasis and shorter survival in TNBC are linked to extensive tumor stroma, emphasizing the importance of selecting effective drugs. Clinical trials compare treatments like carboplatin versus docetaxel for metastatic TNBC, but taxanes show limited efficacy. For advanced stages (III C) resistant to anthracycline-taxane regimens, combinations like Capecitabine with Docetaxel (Taxotere) or Ixabepilone (Ixempra) with Capecitabine are effective. Ixabepilone can also be used as monotherapy [35].

Table 3: Conventional Treatment of Triple Negative Breast Cancer

Conventional Treatment	Drugs	Mechanism	Scheme/Dose
Neoadjuvant treatment Early TNBC (Gold standard) Advanced or Metastatic	Anthracyclines + Taxanes or Capecitabine + Taxane Ixabepilone monotherapy or Ixabepilone + Capecitabine	Cytotoxicity ** Stabilization microtubules	Doxorubicin 20 mg/m ² plus Cyclophosphamide 600 mg/m ² 4 weeks followed by Paclitaxel 80 mg/m ² 12 weeks Capecitabine 1250 mg/m ² 14 days + Docetaxel 75 mg/m ² Ixabepilone 40 mg/m ² per 3 weeks
New neoadjuvant agents (BRCA mutations)	Platinums (Carboplatin) Bevacizumab, Nab-paclitaxel.	Cytotoxicity and VEGF immunotherapy	Adding up standard scheme Abraxane 125 mg/m ² , Carboplatin AUC, Bevacizumab 10 mg/kg
Adjuvant agents	Anthracyclines and Taxanes	Cytotoxicity	Cyclophosphamide 600 mg/m ² + Doxorubicin 20 mg/m ² + Docetaxel 75 mg/m ² for q3 weeks 6 cycles.
Surgery: TNBC, surgical treatment is breast preservation.			
Radiotherapy: radiation therapy (RT) is often given combined or after chemotherapy. RT also could be useful after surgery. Probably benefits in BRCA mutations.			

Surgery

Studies show no significant difference in prognosis or local recurrence between mastectomy and lumpectomy in TNBC. Breast-conserving surgery (lumpectomy) with radiation is a suitable option per National Comprehensive Cancer Network guidelines. However, neoadjuvant therapy is the preferred approach before surgery in TNBC. [36]

Radiotherapy

Radiotherapy is often part of TNBC treatment, especially since TNBC with BRCA-1 mutations is highly radiosensitive. However, there are no specific guidelines for using radiotherapy in TNBC, similar to its pharmacological treatment [37].

Advance Therapeutics

Chemoresistance is a major issue in metastatic cancer treatment, with chemotherapy having side effects and toxicity to normal cells. Two main strategies for targeting therapeutics to tumors are:

Passive Targeting (EPR Effect): This uses leaky blood vessels in tumors to allow nanoparticles to enter, but not all tumors have this feature. Analyzing TNBC biomarkers is needed to target specific receptors like CXCR4.

Active Targeting: This uses biomarkers (e.g., miRNA, proteins, antibodies) and therapeutic molecules (e.g., siRNA, aptamers) to directly target cancer cells.

miRNA

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are gaining importance in cancer treatment due to their potential as diagnostic biomarkers. In TNBC, miR-558 is overexpressed, and several miRNAs have been identified in studies. A key study found 116 deregulated miRNAs in primary TNBC and normal tissues, with miR-106b, miR-17/92 cluster, miR-200 family, miR-21, and miR-155 being highly expressed. Another study linked miRNA profiles to lymph node metastasis, identifying miR-424, miR-125a-5P, miR-627, miR-579, let-7g, and miR-101 as differentially expressed in lymph node tissues. These findings show the potential of miRNAs as powerful biomarkers for diagnosis and prognosis [38].

siRNA

Since the discovery of siRNA's potential, it has revolutionized disease treatment by silencing genes responsible for drug resistance, improving treatment efficacy. In TNBC, siRNA screens identified promising therapeutic targets, such as RSK2, NCAPD2, and Gpx1. These siRNAs have been used in animal models and can be delivered via nanoparticles, viral capsids, or supramolecular complexes to silence genes linked to poor prognosis. Exosomes also play a key role in delivering siRNA to suppress TNBC metastasis, with cationic BSA and siS100A4-loaded exosome nanoparticles helping inhibit tumor growth after surgery [39].

Nanomedicine: Aramdas for TNBC Therapy

Clinically approved nanomedicines like liposomal doxorubicin (Doxil), nab-paclitaxel (Abraxane), and PEG-asparaginase (Oncaspar) are already used in hospitals. Nanomaterials are being studied for their potential to deliver drugs, aptamers, or microRNA to target cancer cells more precisely. Examples of these nanocarriers include micelles, gold nanoparticles, and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs). Nanoparticles can enhance drug delivery, reduce side effects, and improve tumor specificity, making them a promising solution for cancer therapy. Notable advancements include gold nanoparticles for hyperthermia, SPIONs for MRI imaging, and nanocomposites for improved drug delivery. Polymeric nanoparticles like DART are also showing promise in targeting TNBC specifically. These nanotechnologies aim to improve treatment efficacy and minimize systemic toxicity, with more research needed to further optimize their use in cancer therapy[40].

Immunotherapy

The criteria set by Hanahan and Weinberg have evolved over time, adding more functions and properties that help cancer cells grow, invade other tissues, and survive more effectively [41].

Artificial Intelligence

By the late 2010s, artificial intelligence (AI) emerged as a practical tool in various fields, including medicine. In oncology, [42] AI leverages machine learning models for diagnosis and treatment, such as computer-aided detection (CADe), diagnosis (CADx), and explainable AI (XAI). For instance, Seroussi et al. developed DESIREE in 2017, a decision-support system for breast cancer that optimizes treatment plans using metadata validated by oncologists. AI also plays a growing role in breast cancer screening and subtype detection. Recently, Fernández Martínez et al. designed an AI algorithm to identify TNBC subtypes, improving treatment strategies[43]. Future AI systems could integrate databases like TCGA and METABRIC to analyze molecular and clinical data, advancing personalized medicine. Despite its potential, more research is needed to fully realize AI's impact in oncology[44].

Discussion

Breast cancer is a major health concern worldwide. Diagnostic techniques like FNAC (fine-needle aspiration cytology) and CNB (core needle biopsy) are widely used, especially in early stages, and provide accuracy comparable to histopathology. While imaging is effective for screening, FNAC and CNB are crucial for guiding treatment.

The debate over whether cytological (FNAC) or tissue-level (CNB) diagnostics are more accurate remains unresolved, with mixed study results. Recent research emphasizes the importance of clinical judgment in choosing the most effective method.

In our study, FNAC showed a sensitivity of 68.6%, while CNB had a higher sensitivity of 88.1%, a statistically significant difference (OR 0.30, 95% CI [0.21, 0.41], $P < 0.00001$). However, a previous meta-analysis found sensitivities of 72.2% for FNAC and 83.3% for CNB, with no significant difference ($P = 0.13$). This variation suggests that the effectiveness of FNAC and CNB may differ across studies or populations. Further research is needed to understand these differences and identify the most accurate diagnostic method for specific conditions.

Our study included BC patients with suspected metastasis, potentially missing small metastatic foci in sonographically benign lymph nodes using US-FNA. Studies applying FNA to all ultrasound-identified lymph nodes showed similar sensitivity (57%-80%) and specificity (96%-100%) compared to stricter criteria. This suggests broader ultrasound criteria could improve sensitivity without losing specificity. FNAC is more cost-effective than sentinel lymph node biopsy, but

comprehensive cost analyses for its use on all lymph nodes are lacking. While CNB is now the standard in many developed countries for diagnosing breast lesions due to higher accuracy, FNAC remains valuable for its lower cost, less invasiveness, and faster results.

Conclusions

Aberrant signaling in the tumor microenvironment, driven by genomic instability, contributes to suppressed immunity and poor outcomes in TNBC patients. Understanding these signaling pathways is crucial for improving diagnosis and treatment. Molecular therapies targeting genetic and proteomic abnormalities are key to developing effective TNBC treatments. These therapies can be enhanced with agents like aptamers and antibodies to boost efficacy. Additionally, physical therapies such as hyperthermia, photothermal, and photodynamic treatments improve drug delivery to resistant tumor areas. This combined approach offers a comprehensive strategy for eradicating TNBC.

Advances in molecular biology, immunology, nanotechnology, and computer networks are equipping clinicians with better tools for early and accurate diagnoses, enabling personalized treatments. Current research focuses on micro- and nanofluidics to study the tumor microenvironment and cancer dynamics. Nanoelectromechanical (NEMS) and microelectromechanical (MEMS) systems are being used to trace exosomes—cell vesicles with unique surface markers found only in tumors, not in healthy cells. In summary, FNA and CNB are essential tools for diagnosing breast cancer, each with its own strengths. FNA offers higher sensitivity, while both have similar specificity. Despite debates and mixed findings, both methods are vital for diagnosis. Clinical expertise and further research with standardized protocols are needed to enhance accuracy and improve patient care.

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Including cases based on suspected metastasis might have led to non-metastatic cases affecting the results. Variations in needle diameters for US-CNB reflect diverse practices, which may impact comparisons. Additionally, a full cost analysis of performing FNA on all lymph nodes was not done, limiting the evaluation of these diagnostic methods. While TNBC is carried out with different clinical approaches and Surgeries and results variations maybe different in each context accordingly.

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